
LuSEE-Night Conceptual Design Report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

LuSEE-Night is a project to investigate the feasibility of measuring the fundamental physics processes occurring during the cosmic Dark Ages using instrumentation on the lunar surface. The "Dark Ages" refers to the cosmic era between the last scattering of the cosmic microwave background and the time when the first stars and galaxies formed. Only cold, non-luminous hydrogen gas existed during this epoch, and so it has been largely unexplored and remains one of the least constrained frontiers of modern cosmology. The community has therefore shown increasing interest in developing an experimental Dark Ages program based on observations of the hyperfine 21-cm transition of neutral hydrogen, seen against the backlight of the CMB. The global (sky-averaged) spectrum of the redshifted 21cm line is sensitive to the temperature and ionization state of the hydrogen gas and provides a tomographic probe of the thermal history of the early universe, possibly including signatures of new physics beyond the standard model. The recent National Academies ASTRO2020 Panel on Cosmology rated this technique as "...both the discovery area for the next decade and the likely future technique for measuring the initial conditions of the universe in the decades to follow" ([1], p.258).

This document describes a design for a detector that will establish the feasibility of measuring the 21-cm absorption trough in the CMB global spectrum predicted to lie in the highly redshifted frequency range between 4 and 40 MHz. Because of strong terrestrial RFI and ionospheric distortions, this signal cannot be observed from the Earth or from Earth orbit. The detector will therefore be stationed on the lunar surface, on the radio-quiet far side facing away from Earth. To avoid interference from solar RF emissions, observation will take place during the lunar night.

The LuSEE-Night instrument is a radio frequency spectrometer consisting of a set of antennas, analog and digital signal processing electronics, and the necessary mechanical, thermal, communications, and power delivery hardware to support reliable operation on the lunar surface. Four horizontal monopole antennas are arranged to produce wide, zenith-directed beams. As the Moon rotates, the instrument's wide field of view traverses a path covering much of the sky, providing coarse angular resolution. The combination of polarization, spectral, and angular information will provide for offline deconvolution to separate the cosmological signal from much stronger foreground components. Together, the antenna and preamplifier electronics are designed to be sky-noise limited over the 1 - 50 MHz band. Each antenna's output is processed by a signal chain having analog amplification and filtering, and Nyquist-rate digitization. The four channels of digitized data are fed to an FPGA-based "software-defined radio" signal processor that computes auto- and cross-correlation spectra and stores data in nonvolatile memory. Since LuSEE-Night will never be in view of the Earth, the data will be sent back to the science operations center via periodic contact with an orbiting relay satellite (not part of the LuSEE-Night project).

The design of the LuSEE-Night instrument leverages space-proven technology developed for NASA's STEREO/WAVES [2] and Parker Solar Probe/FIELDS [3] missions. These experiments included antennas and spectrometers similar to those needed for this project. To reduce risk and facilitate a highly compressed development schedule, we will adapt the antenna, spectrometer, and power conditioning elements of these predecessor experiments for LuSEE-Night.

For LuSEE-Night to survive on the lunar surface, detailed attention is paid to thermal management. The length of the lunar cycle (29.5 Earth days) and its lack of atmosphere results in extreme surface temperature swings – from 95K at lunar midnight to +390K at lunar noon. The instrument enclosure thus needs both a heat rejection path during the day and a tightly thermally isolated envelope at night. NASA partners will be responsible for these elements of LuSEE-Night. Radiation levels are

non-negligible and COTS electronics will be selected from qualified manufacturers or by upsampling COTS parts. Since radioisotope-based generators will not be permitted, LuSEE-Night will be powered by a battery array for the periods of nighttime observing, which will recharge from a photovoltaic array during each succeeding lunar day.

LuSEE-Night additionally includes a digital calibration source in orbit around the moon. The digital calibrator source emits a known coded broadband signal that can be detected in cross-correlation even when buried in the bright emissions from the Milky Way galaxy and enables precision understanding of the beam pattern and its chromaticity.

The LuSEE-Night instrument consists of elements provided by two DOE labs (Brookhaven and Lawrence Berkeley) and NASA's Space Sciences Laboratory at UC Berkeley. Once assembled and tested, it will be flown to the Moon as a payload element of NASA's Commercial Lunar Payload Services CS3 mission, scheduled for launch in early 2025. Upon successful landing and commissioning, LuSEE-Night will begin operations and expects to deliver about 6 GB of science and telemetry data every lunar cycle, for up to 24 cycles depending on equipment survival.

1 SCIENCE

1.1 DARK AGES COSMOLOGY

The Cosmic Microwave Background is the main pillar of modern observational cosmology. This is radiation released some 400 thousand years after the Big Bang, when the primordial cosmic plasma made of mostly hydrogen and helium atoms immersed in the sea of photons and electrons cools to the temperature at which photons and matter decouple: matter forms neutral hydrogen atoms and light begins to propagate freely through the universe. This same radiation, redshifted to mm wavelengths, is observed today as the CMB. The large distance lever arm of the CMB, and our ability to model the physics using easily solvable linear equations, makes it a truly unique probe, upon which most of the other cosmological probes build upon.

The hundred million years following the formation of the CMB, corresponding to redshifts between $z \sim 1100$ and $z \sim 30$, are referred to as the **Dark Ages**. This is the epoch after the primeval fireball has cooled down, but before the first stars lit up. At these redshifts, cosmological density fluctuations can be directly probed with the 21 cm line whose physics is completely described by well-understood processes governed by gravity, atomic physics, and thermodynamics [4]. Once the first stars begin to form at $z \sim 30$, their emitted radiation alters the neutral hydrogen in the intergalactic medium, which depends on complex non-linear astrophysics, and disallows the first-principles understanding present at previous times. Therefore, the Dark Ages present an incredible opportunity in terms of precision cosmology, essentially free of astrophysical complexity. However, precisely for the same reason, this epoch is not amenable to the traditional surveys used to probe the evolved Universe, which use galaxies or other objects to trace the underlying distribution of matter.

Redshifted 21-cm emission and absorption from neutral hydrogen is **the single known method** that allows, at least in principle, observations of this period in the evolution of the Universe. This emission corresponds to the energy difference between the spins of the electron and proton that are aligned or not aligned in a hydrogen atom. There is no other line in its vicinity and hence it is not easily confused with electromagnetic interaction by other species. The theory of 21 cm emission from the Dark Ages is very well understood: fluctuations in 21 cm emission are sourced by density, temperature and velocity perturbations, which we can calculate from first principles at those redshifts. This has been recognized decades ago [5], but the practicalities are daunting, starting with the fact that the signal is redshifted outside the windows of atmospheric transparency that would allow observations from the Earth's surface. This measurement would, however, provide the holy grail of cosmology, as it probes the same linear physics as CMB experiments, while mapping more three-dimensional Fourier modes of the density field than available in large-scale redshift surveys. This signal has the potential to enable the ultimate sensitivity to the cosmological parameters, including those from early-universe inflation and primordial gravitational waves. However, we have to recognize that this is the end-game that will take decades to develop, should it even prove technically possible.

Another analogy with the CMB is appropriate. The CMB monopole signal (i.e. the CMB itself) was discovered in 1964 by Arno Penzias and Robert Woodrow Wilson for which they received the Nobel Prize in 1978. This discovery was extremely informative and has established the Big Bang theory as the leading cosmological theory. It took another 26 years for the COBE Satellite to measure *spatial fluctuations* in the CMB, for which George Smoot received the Nobel Prize in 2006. It is notable that George Smoot was an employee of the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, illustrating the great science that can be achieved when DOE and NASA collaborate. The discovery of fluctuations and their subsequent characterization with the WMAP and Planck missions cemented the CMB as

Figure 1.1: The predicted 21 cm monopole intensity through cosmic times (plot from [6] in turn adapted from [7]). The lunar farside is the best site to attempt to measure the *Dark Ages dip*, at around $\nu \sim 20$ MHz or equivalently redshift $z \sim 80$.

the cornerstone of cosmological observations. A similar timeline could play out with the Dark Ages 21-cm signal. A detection of the monopole is feasible over the next decade and it would take several decades to work our way towards detection of fluctuations. This would be the arc of a long-term science roadmap towards a new and truly transformational tool for cosmology.

The first stage in the program is the detection of the Dark Ages monopole. Shown in Figure 1.1, this signal is a small dip in the observed radiation intensity as a function of frequency integrated over the entire celestial sphere. It will be detected by measuring a broad absorption trough centered at around 20 MHz. Because the physics is linear and well-understood, we have a prediction for the size and shape of this effect. Any deviation from this template would have immediate and profound implications for fundamental physics. Because there are no astrophysical uncertainties, it would necessarily imply new physics once the possible sources of systematics have been ruled out. The most plausible way of changing the shape and amplitude of this trough is through heating and cooling of the cosmic medium through non-standard processes. Therefore, the Dark Ages dip in the monopole of radiation is the **cosmic calorimeter** that can measure the net energy flows in the baryon fluid. A large number of theoretical proposals exist which can cause deviations from the simplest predictions [8], including dark matter-baryon scattering [9, 10, 11, 12], millicharged dark matter [13, 14], dark-matter annihilation [15, 16], primordial black holes [17], axions [18], neutrino decay, charge sequestration [19], quark nuggets, dark photons [20], interacting dark energy [21] and even a drift in the value of the fundamental constants [22].¹ These are all topics of high interest to the DOE HEP community and can be probed from the lunar surface within the next decade independently of astrophysics. Detection of the monopole would require setting up a low-resolution and high-efficiency radio telescope either stationary on the far side of the Moon or in orbit around the Moon.² Similar to the evolution of the CMB, the path towards detection of the fluctuations would involve working over several decades with radio telescopes of increasing size and complexity on the lunar farside. These instruments will require significant infrastructural development on the Moon, including the provision of power and significant bandwidth. With such a futuristic apparatus, we can hope to detect fluctuations across the sky and thus open a new era of observational cosmology a few decades from now.

¹See Astro2020 Decadal Survey Submission [8].

²A detection of the monopole at 78 MHz, arising from the era of the first stars rather than the Dark Ages, has recently been claimed by an Earth-bound experiment [23], demonstrating the feasibility of such detections with current technology.

Figure 1.2: Figure demonstrating the current state of the inference on the linear power spectrum and a possible reach of the Future Lunar experiment. Adapted from https://github.com/marius311/mpk_compilation/.

As a general probe, a Dark Ages Lunar experiment would be able to probe primordial fluctuations deep into what were linear scales at the time, but which are deep in the non-linear regime today and whose information has been largely lost. This is illustrated in Figure 1.2 which shows how this probe would be transformation both in terms of scales that are probed as well as raw sensitivity. For more information see the science described in the Snowmass paper [24] – while that paper is focused on more near term probes, a Dark Ages experiment would perform much of the same science with orders of magnitude more sensitivity.

1.2 RADIO SKY AT 1-50MHZ

Following the visionary path set up in the previous section will require a decade long program of investment. To enable sound investment, we need to start with a modest experiment that tests the basic assumptions about the observability of the signal. There are three main issues that make this effort challenging:

- **Earth’s Ionosphere and RFI.** The ionosphere severely limits our ability to observe the low-frequency sky from the ground, by modulating signals in frequency as a function of time of arrival that renders any precision observations impossible from the Earth. This motivates observations from the Moon or deep space. Additionally, other sources of low-frequency emission from the Earth, including both man-made (radio emissions as well as sparking in electrical and mechanical devices, and similar sources) and meteorological means that observations from the Moon are best made from its far side.
- **Foregrounds.** Other astrophysical sources of radio emission produce signals which are orders of magnitude stronger. These signals can be distinguished from the signal of interest by their frequency and spatial response differences; however any instrumental leakage from the foreground modes into the signal region through imperfect calibration needs to be understood

Figure 1.3: Figure demonstrating the radio quietness of the far side of the lunar surface as measured by the RAE-2 experiment [25]. "Immersion" and "Emersion" correspond to the satellite orbiting to behind the Moon where it is shielded from solar and Earth's emission.

at the parts-per-million (ppm) level. This requires exquisite calibration, which is particularly difficult from the lunar surface, given our limited control over the observatory. In addition to the very loud galactic emission, the Sun and planets are also loud emitters, whose emission however is characterized by time and frequency variability.

- **Low frequencies.** The radio emission at the frequencies of interest has very long wavelengths that require physically large devices. The wavelength at 10 MHz corresponds to 30m radiation and natural antennas for observations would need to be appropriately sized. Therefore we are mostly working in the short antenna limits with corresponding hits on the antenna sensitivity.

The long term goal is to develop technology that will allow us to make high-precision and high-sensitivity observations from the far side of the moon. This is currently an almost entirely unexplored territory.

The most relevant radio astronomy observations to date were done by the RAE-2 satellite [25], [26], and ground-based measurements by Cane et al. [27]. In Figure 1.3 we show the result from RAE-2 that confirms the expectation that terrestrial RFI in this frequency range is strongly attenuated when the view towards Earth is blocked by the Moon. These early studies also provided models of the galactic foreground spectra, shown in Fig. 1.4.

Figure 1.4: Galactic foreground emission (from [26] [27]). The LuSEE-Night frequency range is shown shaded.

1.3 LUSEE-NIGHT SCIENCE GOALS

The primary goals of LuSEE-Night are to:

- **Establish the Lunar surface as a viable observatory for low-frequency radio astronomy.** There are multiple unknowns regarding observations from the lunar surface. These include the effects of the regolith, constancy of electromagnetic shielding in the presence of magnetic fields, and unknown level of transient phenomena associated with micrometeoritic impacts as well as lunar plasma effects.
- **Perform the most sensitive observations of the radio sky at 1-50MHz.** This frequency regime is motivated by the fact that any observations around the target frequency of ~ 17 MHz will require sufficient lever arm on both sides of the dark ages dip to enable separating the dip from the broadband emission. We aim to make measurements with absolute flux calibration better than 20% across our frequency range.
- **Quantify the systematic effects affecting global spectrum measurement accuracy, and investigate methods to mitigate them.** We will develop models, test procedures and analysis methods to extract the frequency dependence of the antenna beam pattern and signal chain gain, both pre-flight and during operation.
- **Constrain the presence of a non-smooth monopole component at the 10^{-3} level compared to foregrounds.** This is about 3 order of magnitude below the required sensitivity to measure the Dark Ages dip, but will nevertheless be the strongest constraint to date, paving the road for more sensitive future experimental designs.

The system presented in the subsequent sections will have sufficient sensitivity and systematics control to achieve these science goals.

2 INSTRUMENT

2.1 DESIGN OVERVIEW

The LuSEE-Night instrument is a radio frequency spectrometer consisting of a set of antennas, signal processing electronics, power and thermal management hardware, and a communications link for control and data transfer (Fig. 2.1). An orbiting calibration source is planned. The instrument payload will be developed by DOE and NASA partner organizations and delivered to a Commercial Lunar Payload Services (CLPS) provider for integration with a lander and transport to the lunar far side. Radio observations will take place primarily during the lunar night when strong solar emissions are blocked. Data acquired during night observations will be stored to nonvolatile memory and transmitted (via a relay satellite, see Section 3.5) to the mission operations center during the lunar day. We plan for a minimum mission duration of one full lunation (approximately 325 hours of night observing).

Figure 2.1: LuSEE-Night instrument: conceptual block diagram, constraints, and operations concept.

Designing the instrument to deliver the key performance goals of LuSEE-Night means that three significant challenges must be addressed:

- **Surviving the thermal and radiation environment.** The tidal locking of the Moon's rotation to the Earth and its lack of atmosphere result in extreme excursions of the surface temperature from night to day. To prevent overheating or overcooling of the electronics, LuSEE-Night needs special thermal accommodations. Radiation levels are several times higher than those in low Earth orbit, and components must be sourced from qualified parts lists or qualified by the project.
- **Powering during periods of darkness.** With CLPS prohibitions on radioisotope thermal generators (RTGs), the only source of nighttime power will be batteries that are charged during the lunar day by a photovoltaic array. Battery mass constraints thus limit the allowable power consumption of the spectrometer.

- **Self-generated radio frequency interference (RFI).** LuSEE-Night’s spectrometer will be designed to be sensitive to extremely low levels of radiofrequency power. During night operation all inadvertent sources of RF emission will need to be carefully managed. For example, all lander equipment will be totally shut down after commissioning; the RF front end amplifiers will be shielded; and all switching circuitry in the instrument will be slaved to a master clock.

The major elements of the LuSEE-Night instrument are shown in block diagram form in Figure 2.2. The core electronics will be assembled as a sandwich of seven "slices" referred to as the Main Electronics Crate (MEC). The slices include the spectrometer board, a Data Control Board (DCB), an interface to the actuated antennas, and several slices for managing power delivery. The final slice houses the communications User Terminal and S-band transceiver. A 6500 W-hr lithium battery is integrated with the MEC to form the Inner Equipment Assembly (IEA). The IEA will be housed in an outer enclosure providing thermal isolation during the night and heat rejection during the lunar day, see Section 3.3. Mounted to the top of the outer enclosure are:

- four deployable monopole antennas riding on an azimuthal rotation stage, each with its own RF preamplifier (Section 3.1);
- a photovoltaic solar array for daytime powering and battery charging (Section 3.4);
- an S-band patch antenna for communication to the relay satellite (Section 3.5).

Figure 2.2: Internal and external interfaces to the Main Electronics Crate slices.

The major instrument subsystems will be discussed in detail in Section 3.

2.2 OVERALL SYSTEM SPECIFICATION

2.2.1 Key Performance Parameters

The science goals of LuSEE-Night can be met if the system satisfies system parameters listed in Table 2.1, derived as follows:

1. A monopole pair can be operated as a pseudo-dipole and will measure flux and one component of polarization. A second monopole pair will increase the effective aperture and provide a simultaneous measure of the orthogonal polarization.
2. System bandwidth is chosen to include the region where the Dark Ages trough is predicted to exist.
3. Threshold sensitivity corresponds to a sky flux equivalent to the noise contribution of the entire signal chain. The goal is to be sky-noise dominated over the band.
4. Refers to the number of frequency bins computed by the spectrometer. Higher granularity will improve RFI mitigation algorithms.
5. The power consumed by the instrument during night operations. This is dictated by the maximum battery mass.
6. Refers to that portion of the total payload mass (not-to-exceed value of 100kg) allocated to the subsystems provided by the DOE MIE project.

2.2.2 Verification

KPPs 1,5, and 6 can be verified by trivial measurements. The system sensitivity is influenced by features of the lunar surface environment that cannot be replicated in an Earth-based laboratory. The verification of KPP-3 will therefore be based on a set of measurements (feedpoint impedance of the antenna and equivalent input voltage noise density of the front end electronics) and simulations (3D electromagnetic field solvers with appropriate lunar environment parameters) which are input to the sensitivity model. KPP-4 is a parameter in the spectrometer firmware and achieving the objective will depend on the efficiency of the FPGA code.

A preliminary estimate of feasibility is given in Section 2.3.4. In the final design phase more refined models and measurements will be developed and analyzed, and together with component-level measurements will provide validation of this requirement.

KPP#	Parameter	Threshold	Objective	Unit
1	Number of monopole antennas	2	4	-
2	System bandwidth	1-20	0.2 - 50	MHz
3	Instantaneous system sensitivity (central 75% of band)	$< 10^{-20}$	$< 10^{-21}$	$W/m^2/\sqrt{Hz}/sr$
4	Frequency resolution	400	75	kHz
5	Power consumption (avg during obs)	14	12.5	W
6	Mass (DOE MIE subsystems)	85	75	kg

Table 2.1: Key Performance Parameters.

2.3 DESIGN TRADEOFFS AND PRELIMINARY PERFORMANCE ESTIMATE

2.3.1 Instrument Sensitivity

For a first-order estimate let us treat the pair of STACER antennas as an ideal dipole of length L (tip-to-tip) in free space. The flux density received by such an antenna (in $\text{W}/\text{m}^2/\text{Hz}$) at wavelength λ is

$$S_\nu = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2k_B T_{\text{sky}}}{\lambda^2} \right) \int_{\Omega} F(\theta, \phi) d\Omega \quad (2.1)$$

where $F(\theta, \phi)$ is the beam profile and the factor $\frac{1}{2}$ is due to the fact that the dipole only responds to one polarization. Substituting the antenna directivity $D \equiv 4\pi / \int F(\theta, \phi) d\Omega$ we can write

$$S_\nu = \frac{4\pi k_B T}{\lambda^2 D} \quad (2.2)$$

We follow the convention of denoting this by the equivalent noise voltage spectral density e_n in $V/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$, in which case we find the noise-equivalent flux density [28], [29]

$$S_n = \frac{\sqrt{2}e_n^2}{Z_0 Q_{\text{coup}}^2} \quad (2.3)$$

where

- $Z_0 \approx 377\Omega$ is the impedance of vacuum;
- $Q_{\text{coup}} \equiv \ell_{\text{eff}} \cdot \Gamma$;
- $\ell_{\text{eff}} \equiv V_{\text{oc}}/|E|$ is the dipole effective length (ratio of the open-circuit voltage at the feedpoint of the unloaded antenna divided by the magnitude of the electric field along the antenna axis);
- Γ is the power transfer inefficiency due to impedance mismatch between antenna and preamp;

and the factor of $\sqrt{2}$ is due to the uncorrelated noise of the two preamps which are differenced to produce the pseudo-dipole signal in the LuSEE-Night configuration. Since $S_\nu = 4\pi k_B T / D\lambda^2$, we may convert this to the receiver noise temperature

$$T_{\text{rcv}} = \frac{\lambda^2 D e_n^2}{\sqrt{8} k_B Z_0 Q_{\text{coup}}^2} \quad (2.4)$$

The system temperature is therefore

$$T_{\text{sys}} = T_{\text{sky}} + T_{\text{rcv}} \quad (2.5)$$

and by the radiometer equation the uncertainty in the measured signal is

$$\sigma_T = \frac{T_{\text{sys}}}{\sqrt{\Delta\nu\tau}} \quad (2.6)$$

where $\Delta\nu$ is the width of the spectral frequency bin and τ is the integration time.

2.3.2 Coupling efficiency of an ideal dipole and high-impedance amplifier

Next we will consider the factors ℓ_{eff} and Γ making up the transduction efficiency factor Q_{coup} . For an ideal dipole, the effective length is given by

$$\ell_{\text{eff}} = \sqrt{\frac{DR_{\text{rad}}}{\pi Z_0}} \lambda \quad (2.7)$$

where $R_{\text{rad}} = \Re(Z_{\text{ant}})$ is the antenna radiation resistance. In the short dipole regime $L/\lambda \leq .05$ the effective length has a value near $L/2$ and varies slowly with frequency; the variation becomes rapid and non-monotonic as the the frequency approaches the antenna resonances.

We may treat the antenna and amplifier as 1-ports having complex impedances Z_{ant} and Z_{ampl} respectively. When coupled together, the voltage seen by the amplifier equals the antenna open-circuit voltage V_{OC} times the factor

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma &= \frac{Z_{\text{ampl}}}{|Z_{\text{ampl}} + Z_{\text{ant}}|} \\ &\approx \frac{1}{1 + C_{\text{ampl}}/C_{\text{ant}}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

where the second line applies when both the antenna and amplifier impedances are primarily capacitive. This is the case for the electrically-short dipole and a high-impedance JFET source follower preamplifier, and shows the importance of minimizing the stray capacitance at the preamplifier input. When the dipole leaves the electrically-short regime its impedance changes rapidly, changing from capacitive to inductive behavior as it passes through the half-wave resonance at $\lambda = 2L$.

Figure 2.3 shows the behavior of ℓ_{eff} , Γ , and Q_{coup} vs. frequency for three different antenna lengths. Exact expressions for the arbitrary-length ideal dipole have been taken from [30]. The higher coupling efficiency of the longest 12m dipole (green) also has the most resonance features within the LuSEE-Night band. Note too that the maximum coupling efficiency occurs at the half-wave resonance, a well-known result from communication antenna theory.

Figure 2.3: Ideal dipole effective length, mismatch factor, and overall coupling efficiency for $C_{\text{mpl}} = 30 \text{ pF}$ and tip-to-tip length $L = 2, 5, \text{ and } 12 \text{ m}$.

2.3.3 Design tradeoffs

We have identified the first tradeoff in optimizing the LuSEE-Night receiver: the longer the antenna, the more efficient the coupling to the EM field for wavelengths longer than $\sim 20L$. But for the upper end of the L-N frequency band, the antenna length would need to be kept below $\sim 0.3 \text{ m}$ to stay well within the electrically short regime where coupling efficiency is smoothly-behaved with frequency.

Alternatively one could express this as a gain-bandwidth tradeoff, where the useful bandwidth is defined to keep the derivative $\frac{dQ_{\text{coup}}}{d\nu}$ below an acceptable threshold.

In addition to the efficiency-chromaticity tradeoff, an important impact of antenna length is on the the beam pattern. As the L/λ ratio increases, the directivity of the beam first slowly increases and then dramatically changes as the beam develops multiple lobes, Figure 2.4. A highly chromatic beam can cause spatial structure in the sky signal to leak into the inferred frequency spectrum, unless a highly accurate beam model is known. This poses a second optimization of efficiency vs. bandwidth where the bandwidth limit is now set by the frequency above which beam calibration uncertainty causes excessive systematic error on the global spectrum.

Figure 2.4: Beam pattern of an ideal dipole antenna for $L/\lambda = 0.05, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2,$ and 2.5 .

A final tradeoff study concerns optimization of the first transistor in the preamplifier. As shown in Eq. 2.8 the preamp input capacitance should be as low as possible to maximize the impedance match factor in Q_{coup} . To first order, both the input capacitance C_{iss} and the transconductance g_m of a JFET transistor proportional to its gate width, hence reducing the gate width to obtain a better impedance match entails an increase in the equivalent voltage noise density e_n , as well as a reduction in the device’s gain-bandwidth product. Further complicating the choice of input transistor is the need to operate at low bias currents to stay within the subsystem power budget, and the low availability and high cost of space-qualified parts.

In this CDR section we have described the multidimensional trade space for optimizing LuSEE-Night broadband sensitivity, taking the ideal dipole in free space as a model for which analytic expressions for design guidance without requiring complex numerical simulations. For the final design, realistic antenna configurations will be simulated with EM field solvers that will include the characteristics of the actual LuSEE-Night antennas: non-collinear monopole elements, the proximity of the spacecraft and lunar regolith, etc. (Section 3.1). Outputs of the antenna simulations will be used to generate tables of far-field beam patterns and antenna impedances for more detailed engineering and science studies.

2.3.4 Preliminary sensitivity analysis

In this section we present an analysis of a fiducial case with the following assumptions:

- lossless, ideal free-space dipole with antenna length $L=6\text{m}$ (tip-to-tip). This corresponds roughly to a LuSEE-Night configuration with two 3-meter STACERs operated in differential mode as a pseudo-dipole.
- high-impedance preamplifier with $C_{\text{iss}} = 15\text{ pF}$ and $e_n = 1.8\text{ nV}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$. These values are within the range of commercial low-noise JFETs such as IFN112 biased at moderate drain current.
- stray capacitance at preamp input 20 pF . C_{stray} will depend on details of geometry and materials at the antenna-preamp interface which are not known at this time. We also analyze the case $C_{\text{stray}} = 5\text{ pF}$ to show how strongly it affects the SNR.

Figure 2.5 shows the directivity and coupling factors ℓ_{eff} and Γ for the fiducial antenna. As noted above, the coupling maximum occurs around the half-wave resonance.

Figure 2.5: Left: coupling factors for the fiducial case. Right: Beam pattern at four frequencies. The main lobe narrows significantly at 50MHz, corresponding to $L/\lambda = 1.0$.

Figure 2.6 shows the fiducial receiver noise (flux density) for two values of C_{stray} , along with the galactic flux density. The solid (dashed) line shows the threshold (objective) KPP values from Table 2.1. The threshold sensitivity requirement is met with margin for both values of C_{stray} . The objective sensitivity KPP is met at midband, but only extends over the central 20% of the total bandwidth (26% if C_{stray} is reduced to 5 pF).

Figure 2.6: Left: Noise-equivalent flux density for the fiducial case, for 2 values of C_{stray} . Black curves are the galactic flux density models of Cane (solid) and Novaco-Brown (dashed) Right: Signal-to-noise expressed as the ratio of galactic flux to receiver noise, for two values of C_{stray}

This fiducial signal chain model, while highly idealized, provides confidence that the LuSEE-Night

key sensitivity performance parameters can be met.

3 SUBSYSTEMS DESCRIPTION

3.1 ACTUATED ANTENNAS

3.1.1 Overview

The antenna assembly consists of four monopole antennas that are mounted on the four motorized θ rotation platforms. These four units are mounted on the motorized ϕ rotation platform. The CAD image of the conceptual assembly design is shown in Figure 3.1. θ is the angle between a vector that is normal to surface of the local lunar regolith and the monopole antenna, and ϕ is the angle in the plane that is parallel to surface of the local lunar regolith. A study to select lengths of the monopole antennas is currently being conducted to select a length between 1 to 6 meters. The four monopole antennas are assembled 90 degrees from each other to observe two linear polarization states simultaneously. Each monopole antenna is mounted on the separate θ platforms. The θ angles of these platforms will be controlled separately such that θ angles can be positioned accurately with respect to the local ground. The θ rotation platform will be able to rotate $0 \sim 90$ degrees. Actuation of the θ rotation platforms changes the antenna beam profile to enable the systematics study of the antenna beam. A study to select the optimal θ positions to cover interesting beam profiles are being conducted. The ϕ rotation platform will rotate $\pm 90^\circ$ degrees to cover both linear polarization directions with a pair of the antennas. The ϕ rotation platform will be mounted on the outside surface of the LuSEE-Night instrument console. We will use DC servo motors for the rotation stages for the weight and the simplicity of the controller. Positions of rotation stages will be monitored by encoders, and this information will be sent back to the motor controller. The motor controller will be installed inside of the LuSEE-Night instrument console. The motor controller is responsible for drawing power from the PDU, communicating with the RF Comms unit, and sending power and commands to antenna motor.

3.1.2 Antenna

Figure 3.1: (Left) CAD image of the antenna unit. The stacer antenna and the preamp box is mounted on the θ rotation stage. Four θ stages are mounted on the black ϕ rotation platform. Each stage is actuated by DC servo motors. (Right) Photograph of the stacer antenna that was deployed in the STEREO/WAVES experiment [31]

Design of the monopole antenna is based on the "stacer" antenna that was deployed in the STEREO/WAVES experiment [31]. The stacer antennas have been deployed in multiple astrophysics satellite missions used as an antenna or a boom to support an instrument. A stacer is a rolled beryllium copper sheet with a constant helical pitch that acts as a flat spring. It can be compressed

Figure 3.2: (Left) Example of antenna beam profile from HFSS EM simulator. Colors indicate amplitude of the gain of the antenna beam. Simulated structure can be seen inside of the beam. (Right) Example of signal to noise plot as a function of antenna length and frequency.

in a stowed position in a small package until it is deployed. For example, a 6 meter stacer monopole antenna can be stowed in a 53 mm x 106 mm cylinder. Deployment is triggered by actuating a shaped memory array pin with heat. A flywheel and a stacer guide ensures that the stacer antenna is rolled out at a controlled speed. The stacer antennas will be deployed during a lunar day after the landing. The preamp connects to the antenna at base of the antenna. The preamp and the antenna will co-rotate on the platforms.

We are conducting a study to select antenna lengths and θ angles. We are employing three electromagnetic simulator packages, HFSS, CST and FEKO, to simulate how the antenna performs. We are using three electromagnetic (EM) simulators to check whether simulations are set up correctly, and we are also interested in how different simulation algorithms affect the results as HFSS and CST mainly use the finite element method whereas FEKO uses a method of moments algorithm. Considering the weight limitation of the payload, we are constraining our study of the antenna length from 1 meter to 6 meters. We are also constraining our study of the antenna θ angles from 15 degrees to 75 degrees in 15 degree increments. We are modeling the surface of the instrumentation enclosure and the lander as a perfectly conducting polygon (cylinder, box, etc.) as shown in Figure 3.2. The lander vendor is not known at this stage of the project. We are studying the sensitivity of the antenna performance to various shapes and heights of the lander. We are modeling the lunar regolith following recent re-analysis of the Apollo-17 mission data [32]. Still, the low radio frequency properties of lunar regolith on the far side of the moon is not well known. Therefore, we are also varying the dielectric properties of the soil as a function of depth to study the sensitivity of the antenna performance to the properties of the moon regolith. The main outputs of interest from these EM simulators are the antenna impedance, antenna efficiency and the beam profiles as a function of frequency.

These outputs are fed into the analysis pipeline to calculate the raw signal to noise ratio and to calculate the analysis pipeline's ability to extract astrophysical signals. Analysis techniques were based on the methods that were developed and adapted by previous low radio frequency satellite missions and 21 cm astrophysics experiments [33, 34, 35, 36, 28, 29, 37, 38]. Galactic emission is the bright foreground that acts as a reference for the instrument noise. Our goal is to ensure that the instrument achieves photon noise (galactic emission) limited performance. Examples of the analysis are shown in Figure 3.2. The analysis pipeline calculates how our antenna beam observes the radio signals to study how instrument design affects our ability to disentangle foregrounds and

the cosmological signal.

From these simulations, we have found that the optimal position of the antenna is between 2.5 meters to 3.0 meters from the lunar surface. If the antenna is too close to the lunar surface, antenna gain suffers especially at the low frequency end. However, if the antenna is too high off the lunar surface, we observed complex beam shapes due to the interaction of reflected waves from the lunar surface with the antenna. Additionally, consistent with analytical calculations presented in Section 2.3.4, we have found that a longer antenna has higher signal to noise ratio, while suffering from resonances and complex beam patterns. Therefore, we expect the outcome of this study to find a balance between the signal to noise ratio and the complexity of the antenna performance as a function of frequency.

3.1.3 Motorized Stage

The monopole antenna and the preamp will be mounted on the θ rotation stage such that two units rotate together. The four θ rotation stages will be mounted 90 degrees from each other on the single ϕ rotation stage. All stages will be machined out of aluminum. We selected to use DC servo motor over a stepper motor for the weight and complexity of the motor controller. Angle of each motorized stage will be monitored with an encoder. The stages will move during the lunar day when more electrical power is available. Once the stages have reached to the desired angle, they will hold their positions throughout the lunar night for radio quiet observations. The stacer antenna will deploy at the smallest θ angle (sharpest V between monopole antennas). After the ϕ rotation stage rotates through $\pm 90^\circ$, the θ rotation stages will lower the antennas to the next θ angle position. The motors and the motor controller unit will be connected via flexible cable with enough length to accommodate the θ and ϕ rotations. The motor controller will draw power from the PDU, then distribute it to the motors. It will also communicate with the commanding computer to send encoder information and receive move commands. The motor controller will be housed inside of the LuSEE-Night temperature controlled environment.

3.1.4 Integration and Testing

Much of the antenna module can be integrated and tested without interfacing with other modules. For example, the integrated motorized stages can be tested by themselves to check for range of the motion, torque that it can generate, and power draw. The stacer antenna's deployment mechanism can also be tested by itself to check for the operation of the memory alloy pin, and deployment speed. The antenna's EM performance such as antenna impedance can also be checked independently by connecting the antenna to a 4-port Vector Network Analyzer. It will be challenging to make accurate measurements since the antenna will interact with its surroundings in the laboratory setting, but we can utilize techniques to minimize the effect of reflected power such as time gated measurement methods to check whether the port impedance is close to the expected value.

3.2 SPECTROMETER

3.2.1 Description

The LuSEE-Night spectrometer will be an enhanced version of the RF Spectrometer (RFS) flown as part of the FIELDS instrument suite on the Parker Solar Probe ([3], [39]), see Figure 3.3. The new (original) spectrometer acquires spectra over the 0.5 - 50 (0.1 - 20) MHz band from 4 (2) pairs of

monopole antennas using digitizers sampling at 100 (40) Msps and a radiation-tolerant Microsemi RTG4 (RTAX4000SL) FPGA, otherwise retaining much of the structure and processing elements of the earlier design. An overall block diagram of the LuSEE-Night RFS is shown in Figure 3.4.

Figure 4. DCB/RFS FM board. The RFS analog electronics are isolated from the main board in the area in the upper right corner of the DCB/RFS. The DCB FPGA is not shown in this image; when installed, the FPGA resides in the space on the lower left side of the board.

Spectrometer parameter	Experiment	
	Parker RFS (HF channel)	LuSEE-Night
Frequency range	0.01 – 19.2 MHz	0.5 – 50.0 MHz
Digitizer channels	2	4
Sampling clock	39 MSPS	100 MSPS
Duty factor	~1%	~100%
FPGA	RTAX4000	RTG4
Correlation products	2	6
Transient capture	No	Yes

Figure 3.3: Above: The Parker Solar Probe Radiofrequency spectrometer (from [39]), block diagram and PC board layout. Below: modifications for LuSEE-Night.

3.2.2 Analog section

The analog section of the spectrometer is responsible for conditioning the signals from the monopole antennas and forming the signal combinations for digitization. The very front end of the signal chain will be a high-impedance preamplifier whose properties have the dominant influence on the instrument sensitivity. As shown in Section 2.3, the receiver noise temperature will be dominated by (1) the antenna effective length, (2) the power transfer inefficiency due to impedance mismatch between antenna and preamp, and (3) the preamp equivalent input noise spectral density. Over most of the frequency band, both the antenna and preamp impedances will be primarily capacitive, hence the mismatch factor will be that of a capacitive divider $C_{ant}/(C_{ant} + C_{preamp})$ and minimizing C_{preamp} (sum of the gate capacitance of the input FET and any strays) is essential.

The equivalent input noise of the preamp is dominated by the thermal noise of the first transistor plus the noise of any downstream signal chain elements referred back to the input and to first order this can be modeled as a white voltage noise spectral density e_n (in nV/\sqrt{Hz}). Choosing the input transistor's gate dimensions and its bias point entails a performance tradeoff: noise spectral density goes down with larger gate periphery at the cost of higher capacitance, while for a given gate periphery the noise density decreases with higher bias current at the expense of higher power dissipation. This trade space will be investigated through circuit simulation in the final design phase.

Figure 3.4: Spectrometer block diagram showing interfaces to the antenna preamps and Data Control Board.

Figure 3.5: Preamplifier electronics: preliminary design.

Figure 3.5 shows a preliminary LTSPICE schematic and simulation of the preamplifier based on the Parker Solar Probe design. A JFET source follower with ESD protection is followed by a DC block, diode limiter, and 10X gain stage. In the final design the preamp board will include additional elements, such as a programmable gain stage, additional filtering, power regulation, and a 50 Ohm line driver.

Single-ended signals from the four preamps are routed via coax cable to connectors on the frame of the RF Spectrometer slice in the MEC. From there they pass through a multiplexing tree, differential buffer, additional programmable gain stage, and anti-aliasing filter before arriving at the analog-to-digital converter. The arrangement for one ADC channel is shown in Figure 3.6.

The formal performance requirements for the spectrometer analog front end will be established by a flowdown process from the instrument requirements. At the time of this CDR the working assumptions are:

- Input noise: $e_n \sim 2nV/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$
- Capacitance at preamp input: ≤ 30 pF including strays
- 3dB bandwidth: 0.5 - 50 MHz
- Voltage gain: 2 - 1000 in 3 ranges (TBD)
- Preamp power dissipation: 0.5W

Figure 3.6: Antenna multiplexing. Each of the four ADCs can operate on the difference of any pair of antennas, or a single antenna and ground. This arrangement helps cancel common-mode noise, and allows the antenna array to be configured as a pair of pseudo-dipoles.

3.2.3 Digital section

The digital section of the spectrometer includes the multiplexer tree and gain control, digitizers, spectrum processor, snapshot processor, calibration processor, clock management, and interface to the Digital Control Board (DCB). Depending on the observation mode chosen, the multiplexer tree will be set up to pass the difference of antenna pairs (or antenna-ground) to each digitizer. The initial gain range will be automatically set to accommodate the expected signal strength and then adjusted by monitoring the data stream. The frequency plan is to put the LuSEE-Night band within the first Nyquist zone, implying a sampling rate $f_s \geq 100\text{MSPS}$. To adequately cover the expected dynamic range the effective number of bits (ENOB) must be ≥ 11 .

Within the spectrum processor, the elements are:

1. Overrange sensing and gain adjust: when the ADC output is pinned at full scale an algorithm will select the appropriate action: flag or discard the data, reduce analog gain, etc.
2. Decimation filter: if possible, we will oversample the data and use an FIR filter to reduce the complexity of the analog anti-aliasing filter. Depends on the availability of a sufficiently fast ADC.
3. Channelizer and RFI notch filter: a frame of time-sampled data of appropriate length is apodized and processed into a number (256 - 2048) of spectral channels by polyphase filterbank. Each bin's spectral leakage can be tailored by appropriate filter coefficients, and optional notch filter(s) can be incorporated at the frequencies where the RFI 'picket-fence' peaks are expected.
4. Corner turn: data is re-ordered as a matrix transpose to send same-frequency samples from channel pairs to the correlator.
5. Correlator: all auto- and cross-correlations of the four data streams will be calculated (sample-by-sample complex multiplication).

6. Accumulator: the correlation products will be averaged for a programmable integration time, likely in the range of 10s of seconds.
7. Data formatter: at the conclusion of each integration interval the data will be formatted and transferred to the DCB for storage in NV memory.

The snapshot processor will bypass the channelizer and store a frame of raw samples to memory. This mode will be used for detection of transient phenomena and for diagnostics.

The calibration processor will be implemented when the parameters external calibrator details are more fully defined (Section 3.6). The coded sequence in the calibrator will be preloaded into RFS memory and a correlation engine will lock onto the received signal, a technique similar to that used in GPS receivers.

As discussed in Section 2, all switching circuitry in the LuSEE-Night instrument will adhere to strict EMI compliance that forbids switching waveforms that are not slaved to a master clock distributed from the DCB. Within the RFS special care needs to be taken to manage the multiple clocks waveforms needed for operating ADCs, FPGA, and any switched voltage regulators, and to avoid interruptions of return current paths. For further EMI reduction differential signaling, thick ground and power planes, faraday cages around sensitive analog nodes, and EMI gasketing around connectors and apertures may be used.

3.2.4 Monitoring and Telemetry

The spectrometer gain will invariably be temperature- and power supply-sensitive. Gain fluctuations can be mistaken for changes in the sky signal, so it is necessary to monitor and compensate for these effects. The spectrometer board will include thermistors and sense resistors at critical points to monitor temperatures, voltages, and power supply currents. Similar sensors will be included on the preamplifier boards. The analog signals from these sensors will be periodically multiplexed into housekeeping ADCs, sampled, and merged into the instrument data stream. Housekeeping ADCs may be located either on the RFS or the DCB.

3.2.5 Interfaces and Operating Modes

The spectrometer will have interfaces to the Antenna, Power Delivery, and DCB subsystems. The mechanical and electronic details will be formally specified in Interface Control Documents.

Control commands for operation of the spectrometer will come from flight software on the DCB using an industry standard protocol. The DCB will be preprogrammed with standard operating sequences (power-on, sleep/wake, initialize, self-test, acquire [spectra/snapshot/calibration/housekeeping], dump acquired data, etc.) and configuration parameters (gain range setting, multiplexer setting, ADC sample rate, digital filter coefficients, PFB taps/resolution/notch, etc.). During Operation, settings can be modified from the mission operating center by uplink via the relay satellite. Spectrometer data, after averaging, is relatively low volume and can be transferred using moderate-rate interchange formats between the RFS and the DCB.

3.2.6 Component selection and qualification

In general LuSEE-Night's electronics subsystems will use components identical to those used in the Parker Solar Probe FIELDS instrument. For those components which are either unsuitable for L-N or are no longer available, we will seek to use COTS parts which are either:

- rated at Level 3 or above by NASA's Electronic Parts and Packaging Program (<https://nepp.nasa.gov>);
- qualified to MIL-PRF-38535 QML Class V or Class LV-RHA;
- rated by the manufacturer as "Space Enhanced Product (S-EP)".

If no suitable parts from these lists are available, we plan to define a qualification regime for upscreening COTS parts, subject to approval by NASA authorities.

We have identified candidate ADCs and FPGAs for the LuSEE-Night spectrometer, see 3.7. At BNL, we have assembled a test bench and performance testing of some components is underway.

Figure 3.7: Component selection: candidate ADCs (left) and FPGAs (right). Lower left: ADC test bench and performance report

3.3 MECHANICAL & THERMAL DESIGN

3.3.1 Inner Equipment Assembly Mechanical Structure

Figure 3.8 shows the concept design for the instrument. The outer box of the lander will form the overall support structure and will provide layers of thermal insulation to protect inner components. The Inner Equipment Assembly (IEA) of the lander will contain a battery and the Main Electronics Crate (MEC). The battery and MEC will be suspended by Kevlar cables which attach to the corners of the outer box.

Both the electronics and battery will generate heat, which will need to be managed to maintain the acceptable temperature range for the IEA. Heat from the electronics and battery will be transferred to a thermal plate. The plate will connect to a heat pipe which will be attached to an external radiator through a thermal switch. The switch will close during the lunar day and allow heat to be transferred to the radiator, which will then transfer heat to space. During the night, the thermal switch will open, retaining heat within the IEA.

3.3.2 Main Electronics Crate

The design for the MEC will copy what was developed by the Space Sciences Laboratory (SSL) at the University of California, Berkeley (UCB). Images shown in this document are from the CAD model provided by SSL or were from a presentation from SSL [40].

We will reduce project time and risk by using the proven design developed by SSL. This design is currently flying successfully on the Parker Solar Probe. Although we plan to make slight modifications to accommodate different circuit boards, the bulk of the design will remain intact.

Figure 3.8: Concept design for the LuSEE-Night instrument. On top are the four stacers and θ rotation modules, mounted on the ϕ rotation stage. The Battery and MEC are suspended from the outer crate with kevlar cables. On the right is the parabolic radiator panel.

Figure 3.9: *Left panel:* Main Electronics Crate (MEC) showing individual slices. Solid model courtesy of SSL. *Right panel:* Tie Rods in the Main Electronics Crate (MEC) that compress all slices. Solid model courtesy of SSL.

Figure 3.10: *Left Panel:* Electronics board mounted in a frame. *Right Panel:* Cross-sectional view of slices showing PCBs, EMI shields, and interlocking geometry on the edge of each frame.

The Main Electronics Crate, shown in Figure 3.9 will consist of individual “slices” that are composed of frames which house individual printed circuit boards (PCBs), electromagnetic interference (EMI) shields, connectors, and vacuum vents. There will be six of these slices held together with tie rods or “skewers”, shown in the right panel of Figure 3.9 . The entire assembly will be fastened to a mounting plate or battery housing, and between the plate and MEC will be a thermally and electrically conductive gasket material. The gasket material will provide a path to conduct heat from the MEC as well as grounding. All electrical connections will be made outside of individual crates, simplifying assembly and testing. The modular design, along with outer connectors, allows individual slices to be removed or added to the stack as needed.

The left panel of Figure 3.10 shows how the PCBs are mounted in each frame. Behind the PCB (not shown) is an EMI shield. The right panel of the same figure shows that when slices are stacked each PCB is protected on both front and back by EMI shields. Along with the compression placed on the frame by the tie rods, interlocking features on each frame keep slices fixed relative to each other.

Each electronic board will be attached to frames using screws and custom retainers designed by UCB that have a Spiralock® thread which will prevent the screws from loosening. Spiralock threads are used elsewhere in the assembly for the same reason. The circuit boards will have a conductive ground plane on the edges which will transfer heat away from the PCB to the frame of each slice. From each frame, the heat will transfer through the mounting plate and heat pipe to a radiator on the outside of the instrument structure.

Connectors on frames will be retained by custom retainers developed by UCB, shown in the left panel of Figure 3.11 . These retainers also have Spiralock® tapped holes to prevent the retaining screws from loosening. The right panel of the same figure shows a vent feature that will be installed on each slice and allow any gasses inside to vent to space.

The mass budget for the Inner Box is shown in Figure 3.12. The mass for the total instrument is estimated to be 87.5 kg, not to exceed 100 kg. The IEA is expected to have a mass of 55.5 kg, mostly from the 45 kg battery. The crates will each have a mass of approximately 1 kg, and mounting plates and wire harnesses will make up the remaining mass.

Figure 3.12 also shows calculated power consumption during daytime and nighttime operations. During the day, the amount of power consumed is estimated to be 50.8 W. An estimated 28.3 W will be converted to heat inside the IEA. The remaining power will be converted to stored energy in the battery or lost through the preamplifiers and communication antenna, both outside of the IEA. At

Figure 3.11: *Left Panel:* Custom retainer developed by UCB. Image courtesy of UCB. *Right Panel:* Image of a vacuum vent used for each slice.

LuSEE-Night	mass [kg]	night power [W]	day power [W]
IEA (inner box)	55.5	10.4	48.8
PPT	1	0	1
PDU	1	0.1	0.1
DCB	1	2	2
PF-PS	1	3	3
MO-DE & AEB	1	0.1	0.1
Spectrometer	1	5.2	5.2
RFCOMM	1	0	20
Inner BOX harness	1.5		
Battery	45		17.4
heat transfer plate	0.5		
mounting plate	1.5		
Outer BOX	5		
Lander Interface Bracket (LIB)			
mounting feet			
Attachments	27	2	2
Sci-Antenna	10		
PREAMP	0	2	2
Solar array	5		
Comm-Antenna	4		
Radiator	5		
attachment harness	3		
NTE	100.0	14.0	100.0
CBE	87.5	12.4	50.8
CBE thermal		12.4	30.3

Figure 3.12: Summary of mass and power budget allocation separated by day and night operations.

night, the total power consumption is estimated to be 12.4 W. The preamplifiers outside the IEA will consume 2 W of this power. An estimated 10.4 W will be used by electronics and converted to heat in the IEA.

3.3.3 Main Electronics Crate Thermal Design

Potential landing sites for the LuSEE project play a major factor in the survivability of the onboard electronics. Surface temperatures at different latitudes of the lunar surface can vary up to nearly 225 K at the same time of day. It is important to rule out latitudes on the lunar surface that may be too hot during the lunar day for the electronics. Potential onboard electronics have a survivability range of 213.15 K to 313.15 K.

The *Planetary and Lunar Environment Thermal Toolbox Elements (PALETTE) Project Year One Results* and *The global surface temperatures of the Moon as measured by the Diviner Lunar Radiometer*

Figure 3.13: LuSEE experiment mounted on example lunar lander.

Experiment papers were used to determine the conditions on the lunar surface and their effect on the LuSEE lander.

Suppose the Lander/LuSEE experiment is designed as depicted in Figure 3.13. Given this orientation, features such as the lander, solar panel, and the radiator would obstruct even distribution of solar and lunar irradiation.

Boundary Conditions

Figure 3.14 summarizes the incident radiation on the LuSEE outer crate, from the Sun and the hot lunar surface. Effected surface area of the two different sources of radiation was determined to be an even split, with the top half of the crate experiencing solar radiation and the bottom half experiencing radiation from the lunar surface or from the lander, which will not be significantly thermally isolated from the lunar surface, and is expected by PALETTE to have a temperature only marginally below that of the lunar surface (see calculations below). The effected surface area can be further refined by accounting for the solar panel and radiator. The solar panel blocks an entire face of the outer crate's surface area effected by solar radiation. Similarly, the radiator is assumed to block another face of the crate, however this face would have experienced solar radiation on the upper half and lunar surface radiation on the lower half.

LuSEE current best estimates for power consumption have been estimated to be as much as 45 W during the day. Some of this power goes to charging the battery and some to electronics outside of the outer crate, such as the PREAMP and Science Antenna. After accounting for charging power and outer electronics, the inner electronics crate is estimated to use about 32.15 W during the day. The full 45 W was used for the thermal calculations.

A thermal switch, of unknown composition, transfers heat between the science payload and the radiator. The radiator, of unknown size and efficiency, then radiates the heat into space. PALETTE states that the PTA thermal switch has an ON/OFF ratio of at least 2500:1. The PALETTE document lists the conductance of the thermal switch, in the off position, as 0.002 W/K. PALETTE does not elaborate on whether the conductance is for the Primary Thermal Architecture (PTA) or the Backup Thermal Architecture (BTA) thermal switch, but it is assumed to be PTA as the figure in section 3, Technology, illustrates a PTA thermal switching system. This would then suggest that the

Figure 3.14: Summary of radiation incident on LuSEE experiment.

conductance of the thermal switch, in the on position, should be 2500x the conductance of the off position. (5 W/K)

The PALETTE lists the surface area of their radiator as 0.165 m^2 . Knowing that the total surface area of the LuSEE experiment is 63% bigger than that of the experiment in the PALETTE document, a radiator surface area of 1.63 times that of the PALETTE's was assumed (0.2695 m^2).

Temperature of the lunar surface changes with the moon's latitude. The surface temperature is highest at the equator and decreases towards the poles. The global surface temperatures of the Moon as measured by the Diviner Lunar Radiometer Experiment article states that the maximum temperature of the lunar surface, at the equator, is 392.3K. A value of 400K was used for calculations.

It is understood that the radiator emits heat through radiation towards the sky which is assumed to be 10 K.

Daytime Thermal Calculation

An assumption had to be made for the temperature of the outer box due to an abundance of unknowns, such as the composition of the lander, the thermal isolators that the LuSEE Experiment will be mounted on, and the composition of the outer box of the experiment. The PALETTE document lists the temperature of their lander as 353 K, so this value was used as the steady state temperature of LuSEE's outer box during lunar day.

Figure 3.15 shows the thermal pathway that was determined as the basis of the heat transfer calculations. Because the temperature at position 3 was assumed, the calculations solve for the temperatures between points 3 and 6.

An iterative solver was used to find the temperatures for positions 4 and 5. The results of the calculations (see Figure 3.16) show that the LuSEE experiment could survive lunar day temperatures at the equator if a heat pipe with a conductance of 5 W/K were coupled to a radiator of similar efficiency to that of the PALETTE document, and a radiative surface area of 0.2695 m^2 . This suggests that, given similar conditions, the experiment would not have to rule out any specific latitudes for landing options out of any thermal concerns. In summary, the IEA temperature of 265K falls within the survivability range of 213.15K to 313.15K.

A simple check can be done to confirm the accuracy of these calculations. For instance a simple

Figure 3.15: Thermal path through lunar lander and LuSEE experiment, including: (1) the lunar surface, (2) the lander body, (3) the outer enclosure, (4) the Inner Equipment Assembly, (5) the radiator, and (6) the sky.

$q = G\Delta T$ calculation can be done to confirm that the product of the heat pipe's conductance (5 W/K) and the change in temperature of points 4 and 5 does indeed equal the given 45 W from the battery.

Nighttime Thermal Calculation

Similar calculations must be made to determine the survivability of the experiment during the lunar nighttime. Temperatures of the lunar surface drop to as little as 85K during the nighttime and without the incident radiation of the sun, the lander assembly gets very cold. Without proper adjustments, the temperature of the electronics can fall outside of the survivability range.

At night, the operations of the IEA change and only 12.4W are used by the battery. So, 12.4W was used in the calculations as heat generated by the system. A lunar surface temperature of 85K was used (Williams et. al), and the PALETTE document was referenced to assume a lunar lander temperature of 75K.

If no changes are made to the assembly between daytime and nighttime, the radiator will emit too much heat and the IEA will get too cold. The PALETTE document states that the conductance of

Figure 3.16: Thermal architecture and calculation results for LuSEE experiment.

their thermal heat pipe changes from an ON to an OFF position when lunar night comes around. The document lists an OFF conductance of 0.002 W/K. We found this conductance to be too low and causes the IEA to heat up past its survivability range. The tension cables and the multilayer insulation are too effective and trap the heat generated by the battery.

For the IEA to maintain a calculated nighttime temperature of 264.5K, which is just about the median of the survivability range (213.15 to 313.15 K), the conductance of the heat pipe must change from 5 W/K (daytime) to 0.15 W/K.

3.3.4 Preamplifier Box Thermal Design

To ensure the survivability of the LuSEE electronics, a thermal analysis of the preamplifier in lunar daytime was performed. This analysis expanded on the LuSEE lander thermal analysis and introduced preamplifier geometry, preamplifier power generation, and an MLI blanket. LuSEE's current best estimate for power consumption, Q_{preamp} is 0.5 W from the preamplifier. The preamplifier was estimated to be 0.02 x 0.05 x 0.085 meters in size, where both the top and bottom surfaces had a surface area of 0.0045 m². Full contact was assumed on the bottom side of the preamplifier to the outer crate and the top surface of the preamplifier to the MLI blanket. The MLI blanket was estimated to have 90% reflectivity with a conductive property of 10⁻⁵ W/mK on the low value and 26.24 W/mK on the high value. The conductive property for the outer crate to the preamplifier was evaluated for aluminum to aluminum, with a low estimate of 167 W/mK and a high estimate of 235 W/mK. High and low estimated values for MLI reflectivity, conductivity and outer crate conductivity were analyzed to find a threshold temperature of the preamplifier. The emissivity of MLI was 0.02 and was used to calculate the energy radiating out of the MLI to the environment, Q_{env} . The solar radiance was 1361 W/m² and with the area exposed, was used to solve the solar radiation going into the MLI blanket.

An iterative solver was used to find the temperatures for positions 2 and 3 of the thermal path shown in Figure 3.17. The results of the calculations show that the preamplifier temperature did not vary greatly from the outer crate temperature. The temperature deviance was $\pm 1\text{K}$ when analyzing the high and low estimates for reflectance and conductance. The temperature variance from the outer crate's known temperature to the preamplifier temperature could be a result of full contact assumption with a 0.0045 m² surface area, and no additional mount from the preamplifier to the outer crate. The compact geometry, and small power generation of the preamplifier, combined with the calculated values of solar energy absorbed and energy leaving the MLI to the environment, are

Figure 3.17: *Left panel:*The thermal pathway that was determined as the basis of the heat transfer calculations for the preamplifier. Point (1) is the IEA, (2) is the preamplifier, (3) is an MLI blanket over the preamplifier, and (4) is the sky. *Right Panel:* The thermal calculation results.

also considerations for the temperature variance. This suggests that the outer crate controls the preamplifier temperature under the investigated circumstances. If the preamplifier is capable of surviving expected outer crate temperatures during lunar daytime, an additional analysis should be performed to further investigate if the preamplifier electronics can survive lunar nighttime.

Similar calculations have been done for the nighttime thermal preamplifier analysis. This analysis expanded on the main electronics crate nighttime thermal analysis. The preamplifier operated with 0.5W of power, and the full side contact was assumed from the outer crate and to the MLI blanket. The iterative solver used in the daytime was also used in the nighttime and the preamplifier temperature was calculated to 93.9K. This temperature was mainly determined by the outer crate temperature. If the preamplifier electronics are not rated to survive this temperature in the nighttime, an additional analysis should be performed for additional geometry that would limit the amount of contact between the outer crate and the preamplifier.

3.3.5 Shipping Container

The shipping container has not yet been designed, and this effort will occur later in the project. Several years ago, BNL designed a shipping crate for part of the camera on the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST). The Inner Equipment Assembly will be roughly the same size as what was shipped for LSST, so we will have a good starting point for our design.

3.4 POWER DELIVERY

LuSEE-Night has to operate during the lunar night that is 14 Earth days (336 hours) long. During this time the onboard battery will provide power to the electronics and will be gradually depleted until the next sun rise when power from the photovoltaic panel will power the electronics and recharge the battery for the next night. This process is outlined in Figure 3.18

The components of the power delivery subsystem are shown in Figure 2.2 and include the battery, the photovoltaic panel, its associated peak power tracker (PPT), the power distribution unit (PDU) and the low noise picket fence power supply (PF-PS). The battery will provide the main bus power

Figure 3.18: Plot of power consumption, solar power production and charge state of the battery as a function of the lunar night/day cycle.

to the PDU unit which can route power for the various other slices of the MEC. For the startup of operations, when power is initially available, the PDU it will route power to the DCB to boot and manage further operation from withing the DCB software control. The DCB will then instruct the PDU to route power to the PF-PS to provide clean power and synchronize the systems DC/DC converters from battery to PF-PS. When clean power is available, the DCB will instruct the PDU to power up the spectrometer and the antenna slice. This would be the configuration for night time operation. The battery provides telemetry to the DCB, such that the charge and discharge current, the state of charge (SOC), and the temperature are always known and the onboard software can act accordingly.

During day the PPT will find the optimum operating point for the photovoltaic cells and provide that power to the battery where the battery build in BMS will use some of the power to power the main bus and some of the power to charge the battery cells. When the DCB telemetry indicates that sufficient solar power is available it will instruct the PDU to route power to the RF-Radio for communication (see communication subsection) in addition to the battery being charged. For the corner case where the battery is too cold to be efficiently charged, power from the photovoltaic cells will be used to first heat the battery with a resistive heater and the battery will start charging once it reaches a suitable temperature. The current best estimate (CBE) for power consumption of the various components is shown in Figure 3.12. During the night we expect a power draw of 12.4W over a duration of 384h, which is a total period of 16 Earth days and includes an extra time of 24h for dusk and dawn, where the power generated would be insufficient. During the remaining 288h the system will require an average of 17.4W of power to charge the battery (95% efficiency assumed) plus the power consumption of the electronics and the RF-radio, estimated to be an effective total and conservative estimate of 50.8W. If needed for thermal control (not to overheat) or for power management (insufficient solar power) the DCB software can control the various parts of LuSEE-Night and un-power the spectrometer and preamps or power the RF-radio only when communication is expected (as shown in Figure 3.18). Using average performance data from space grade photovoltaic panel vendors LuSEE-Night will need a minimum of 0.36m² of solar

cells. The exact size of the panel will be determined with margin management and more detailed simulations of LuSEE at the proposed landing site.

3.5 COMMUNICATION

LuSEE will be stationed on the far side of the Moon. Due to Moon's tidally-locked orbit, it's angular velocity around the earth matches the angular velocity around its own axis. Consequently the Moon faces the Earth with the same hemisphere, but the entire Moon-Earth system rotates with respect to the Sun. Both near and far lunar hemispheres experience ordinary lunar "days" with a full solar cycle (time between subsequent solar transits) of about 29.5 Earth days and lunar sidereal cycle of about 27.3 Earth days (time between subsequent transits of a distant star).

This cycle defined the basic observational pattern of the LuSEE-Night experiment. We perform ultra-quiet lunar night-time observation for about 15 earth days, followed by the lunar day-time 15 earth days, during which we recharge the batteries and perform communications with the Earth. These communications will involve the full download of the data as well as housekeeping information. It will also involve uploading the system configuration for the next observing run. Since there are approximately two earth weeks during this period, the results of the previous night's observation will likely influence settings and configuration for the subsequent night operation.

Because the lander will be located on the far side of the moon, the communication will necessarily be performed via the relay satellite. The current plan is to use the European Space Agency's Lunar Pathfinder Satellite³ (LPF). LPF is a first step towards ESA's ambitious Moonlight vision to create a network of communications and data relay satellites serving users worldwide. It is a dedicated mission to the moon to provide communication capabilities to assets on the far lunar side in S-band and X-band. It is currently scheduled to launch on the same rocket that will deliver CS-3 mission on which the LuSEE-Night will reside.

LPF is built by the Surrey Space Technologies SSTL and will be operated commercially. That is, most actors will have to acquire appropriate bandwidth by negotiation with SSTL. LPF will operate by default in a store-and-forward mode in which the data will be exchanged with the lunar asset at appropriate times and communicated to Earth later.

LPF will be delivered into a high elliptical inclined frozen orbit. Majority of orbits around the Moon are unstable, but a small set of orbital inclinations are naturally stable. LPF's orbit will be elliptical so that it will spend majority of the time serving the lunar southern hemisphere which is believed to be commercially more interesting.

The lander of CS-3 will also carry a Jet Propulsion Lab (JPL) user terminal which will be used to commission the LPF communication capabilities. It will be an S-band receiver system. LuSEE-Night will rely on a clone of the JPL system, using the same radio and software, but a different antenna.

Our current design involves a medium gain patch antenna located at the top of the turntable and 4W emission power. The total bandwidth will be of course dominated by the data download from the instrument to earth, since the configuration packets are rather modest in size.

To estimate the feasibility of this plan we have estimated our data needs and then compared those to the total available bandwidth. This calculation was done as follows.

The minimum estimated data transfer is as follows. If raw data are averaged in the instrument over timescales that are too long, the sky signal will be smeared, leading to a loss of information.

³<https://bsgn.esa.int/service/lunar-pathfinder/>

Item	Size (GB)	Comment
Main auto and cross-power spectra	1-2	16 power spectra, every 30s, 1024 spectral bins, 2 bytes per bin
Additional power spectra	1-4	self-subtracted data, outlier corrected spectra, high-res spectra
House-keeping data	0.5	200 sensors, every second at 2 bytes per reading
raw-data streams	1-2	both raw ADC samples, unaveraged raw PFB samples
Total	3.5 - 8.5	Total data per night.

Table 3.1: The total data payload size for individual lunar night.

On the other hand, if the integration is too short, we are transmitting data that is noisier than any temporal changes in signal, leading to inefficient use of bandwidth. This lead to a condition that

$$\Delta t \sim \left(\left(\frac{d \log T}{dt} \right)^2 B \right)^{-1/3}, \quad (3.1)$$

where δt is the integration time, $\frac{d \log T}{dt}$ is the logarithmic rate of change of signal due to Moon's rotation and B is the bandwidth of a bin. Using plausible assumptions this lead to $\Delta t \sim 1$ min that further leads to about 500MB of data for 15 day integration. Of course, this is an absolute minimum without any housekeeping. In practice, we want to sample at finer resolutions, add significant amounts of house-keeping data as well as raw data segments, self-subtracted power spectra, etc that will help us better understand that system performance and calibration issues. Table 3.1 describes currently envisioned data payload volumes. In short, the science requirement is that at least 3.5GB of data are transferred every lunar day. By using more aggressive lossy compression it would be possible to reduce data payload to 1GB. At data volumes below 1GB per lunar day, the science will start to become seriously impacted. On the other hand, there is almost no upper limit on how much data we can transfer that will bring some value to the project as described next.

The valuable commodity is the bandwidth to Earth rather than the actual data storage. We therefore plan to have significantly more storage than the available bandwidth. The current plan is to have 128GB of solid state storage and total daily payloads of 64GB. Each night's total payload will be available for the day following the observations and one more subsequent lunar day. The total payload will consist of a small "always-transfer" portion and further data that will be transferred upon request. For example, based on how the data looks, we might decide to download further data which are either more finely averaged in time or frequency or some other combination.

To understand the total available bandwidth, we have performed the following calculation. We have assumed a nominal frozen orbit for the LPF and neglected any perturbation. We have assumed a 4W emitted power feeding a medium gain antenna at LuSEE-night with the following gain factors: 6.5dBi at zenith, dropping to 4.5dBi at 30° from zenith and 0dBi at 60° from zenith. We have assumed that no data transfer take place if satellite is more than 60° from zenith. We have then re-implemented the link margin calculation from the SSTL provided spreadsheet. This calculation takes into account various errors in pointing (the satellite antenna actively points at the asset on the Moon) and then based on the total gain and distance calculates link margin for each raw bit rate. Following SSTL specification we assumed that raw bit rates are quantized in powers of two with the maximum bitrate of 2048Mbps and that bit rates can adapt dynamically as the satellite tracks across the sky. The coded bit rate is 66% of the raw-bit rate and is the available bandwidth for data transfer. We assume we can transfer during the 12 central days of each lunar day. Results of

Figure 3.19: Total transfer volumes as a function of the phase of the LPF orbit for different landing latitudes. This shows the variations of the total available bandwidth during different days, i.e. each day will correspond to a particular value of LPF phase. See text for discussion.

this exercise are plotted in Figure 3.19. We see that in all cases the total available volume exceeds our needs. Interestingly, for southern locations, the data transfers is generally higher but also varies considerably from day to day. The equator locations provide a good margin in the available bandwidth, although what fraction of the total theoretically available bandwidth will be available to us remains to be determined.

3.6 CALIBRATOR

Accurate calibration of the LuSEE-Night instrument is essential for identifying and separating the flux from foreground sources from the cosmological 21cm signal. For a successful analysis, both absolute and relative calibration vectors must be understood.

The *absolute calibration* allows us to associate the total energy transfer from the sky to the antenna system in $W/m^2/Hz$ units or equivalently in Kelvin (assuming Rayleigh-Jeans conversion factor) as is commonly done in radio astronomy. This is very difficult to do with high precision, due to many unknowns. For example, the coupling of our antennas to the ground is unknown at percent level, because it depends on the dielectric constant of the lunar regolith. Moreover, the effects of reflective structures in the lander on the beam have to be modeled using electromagnetic simulators; these are again typically accurate at around a few percent level. Our main level to understand these effects is to measure the same sky using different antenna configurations. Antenna azimuth and elevation will modulate the effects of the ground and other structures in a unique fashion. Because the sky being observed is the same, this would allow us to break degeneracies and establishing the absolute accuracy of the beam model by comparing expectations given EM simulations with the data while making only weak assumptions about the sky signal. We estimate that this would allow us to understand the overall antenna effects at 1-10% level. The second uncertainty is the shape of signal propagation through the front-end amplifier and electronics to the digital subsystem. The main uncertainty here is the stray capacitance which directly affects the coupling of antenna to front-end amplifier. The response of the rest of the signal chain will be

Figure 3.20: Left: Coverage of a beam at latitude -10° assuming a calibration on the Lunar Pathfinder orbit. Right: Block diagram for the calibrator electronics board.

carefully measured in the laboratory as a function of temperature recorded at crucial positions along the signal chain. We hope to establish an absolute overall gain at the percent level. Overall, without imposing external data beyond system simulation we think that establishing absolute calibration at the 20% level is feasible.

Existence of external data will help us improve these measurements. One of the main standard calibrations is our own galaxy, which has been measured at these frequencies in the 1970s. The RAE-2 experiment [25] in orbit around the Moon and the ground based measurements of [27] provide consistent measurements with 10% absolute accuracy. These measurement will be an important cross-check. Moreover, radio emission from Jupiter varies temporally at the 10% level, but its long-term average is predictable to better accuracy. Jupiter is additionally a unique polarized radio source on the sky.

The *relative calibration* refers to our ability to constrain the ratio of fluxes at two different frequencies. In principle this is easier than absolute calibration, because the overall gain changes cancel out. Nevertheless it is still a daunting prospect for many of the same reasons that affect the absolute calibration determination. Moreover, because we are ultimately interested in measuring the Dark Ages trough, we are not interested in relative calibration vectors that correspond to variations over the band that are smoother than the Dark Ages trough.

In terms of system design, our main insurance is the small electrical scale of the antennas, which ensures that the antenna spectral responses are slowly varying as a function of frequency. In general structures that are at physical distance L , will generate standing waves for $N\lambda = L$, imprinting oscillatory structure in the antenna response at $\Delta\nu = c/L$. Given that our overall system size is $O(10m)$, which gives $\Delta\nu \sim 30$ MHz, which is more slowly varying than the Dark Ages trough, but not by much. After marginalizing over a slowly varying gain vector and again seeking consistency after modifying antenna azimuth and elevation parameters we think that it is feasible to establish percent level relative calibration uncertainty from first principles.

To go beyond that we will employ an external calibrator on a satellite. This calibrator will act as a known source providing both absolute and relative sky calibration. Any satellite in a low moon orbit will provide a good coverage of our beam in multiple directions as well as cross linking. This is show in the left panel of Figure 3.20 for a representative orbit. The right panel of the same figure shows the block diagram for the electronic board of this component. The total calibrator payload

includes a 1kg electronics board as well as 1kg antenna package as four 1m stacer antennas.

The calibrator works by providing a known signal that is detected in cross-correlation on the receiving end. The total power consumption is 10W, of which radiated power is 0.2W. In cross-correlation at the receiver this gives sufficient signal to noise to allow integration without explicit Doppler corrections. This is sufficient to map the spectral and spatial response of our beam to high accuracy. The strong cross-linking (probing the same point in the receiving beam) from multiple orbits and orientations of the emitting beam would allow us to solve simultaneously for the emitting beam shape as well as the receiving beam shape. Together with overall system simulations this would allow us to understand the beam systematics to better than the 10^{-3} level. We note that the calibrator does not need to be launched concurrently with the main LuSEE payload. As long as the firmware on the spectrometer is capable on detecting and latching on to the calibrator, useful information will come as long as there is an overlap in the mission duration. Finally, for long-lived missions, the same calibrator could provide service to subsequent missions.

We are currently in discussion with NASA regarding possible platforms on which the calibrator could be flown. Several possibilities have been identified. The subsequent development of the calibration plan is pending identification of the appropriate vehicle to carry the calibrator.

4 ASSEMBLY, INTEGRATION & TESTING

Quality assurance for LuSEE-Night includes verification and validation procedures undertaken at various points during the instrument build. The sequence is illustrated diagrammatically in Figure 4.1.

Detailed component and subsystem requirements documents will be the basis for verification testing. Tests may include functional and performance measurements. Depending on the component, both electronic and environmental (thermal, vibration) tests may be required. The first verification step, for engineering (EM) and flight model (FM) components, will be done at the subsystem teams' site. For the EM components, these tests must be completed by the time of the Final Design Review currently scheduled for March 2023, which will coincide with a Production Readiness Review (Step 1 in Figure 4.1). The FM components are then manufactured and the component-level qualification tests of Step 1 are repeated (September 2023). At BNL, the MEC slices are then assembled and integrated and the crate is tested on the bench, and the MEC and battery are integrated into the inner mechanical box to form the IEA FM subassembly. We plan to make a temporary hookup of the IEC with preamps, rotation stage, and comms antenna and perform a functional bench test during Fall 2023 (Step 3). A pre-ship review is scheduled for January 2024, when the results of the bench test of the IEC will be reviewed. Shipment of the DOE deliverables (IEC, antennas, and rotation stage) to SSL is scheduled for March 2024, at which point the DOE MIE project is concluded.

After completion of the MIE, the full LuSEE-Night instrument is integrated with the NASA deliverables (outer enclosure with thermal management) at SSL (step 4) followed by shipment to the CLPS lander vendor. The CLPS vendor will verify that the instrument conforms to all accommodations agreed to in Appendix A, integrate LuSEE-Night and additional payloads with the lander's mechanical, electrical, and thermal systems, and perform final tests (step 5) before transport to the launch site. The completed lander will then move to the launch site and undergo final pre-launch tests (step 6). The CS-3 CLPS launch date is currently scheduled for early 2025.

It is expected that LuSEE-Night personnel will play an active role in final instrument tests at SSL, vendor, and launch sites. See the following Section for a discussion of tests planned during transit,

Figure 4.1: Sequence of integration and test steps: (1) component test, (2) test of integrated Main Electronics Crate), (3) lashup of IEA, preamps, rotation stage, and comm antenna, (4) integration and test of full LuSEE-Night instrument, (5) integration at CLPS lander vendor, (6) pre-launch final functional test. Steps 4-6 occur after completion of the DOE MIE project in March 2024.

commissioning, and early operations on the lunar surface.

5 CONCEPT OF OPERATIONS

5.1 LUSEE COMMISSIONING ON THE LUNAR SURFACE

On the lunar surface and shortly after landing, LuSEE requires a short period of aliveness testing. This will involve the application of LuSEE operational power by the Lander PDU.

The LuSEE internal deployment power bus shall remain safe – unpowered – during all mission phases in which deployments are not planned. That includes times when the LuSEE MEP itself is powered.

The Lander shall provide for low-latency (<1 minute latency) LuSEE telemetry and telecommands to and from earth. Telemetry data will be sent by LuSEE to the Lander and then to the Lander’s MOC from which it will flow to the LuSEE SOC. The LuSEE SOC will run commissioning procedures to generate and send telecommand sequences to verify the nominal functioning of the LuSEE instrument.

5.2 DEPLOYMENTS

On the lunar surface with basic functionality verified, LuSEE requires a period for the deployment of its appendages. The LuSEE team will develop deployment procedures to use in activating and verifying nominal functioning of the instrument followed by the deployment of its appendages. These procedures will require low-latency (<1 minute latency) real-time bi-directional telemetry and telecommands between the LuSEE SOC and the LuSEE instrument.

The Lander shall facilitate the start of the LuSEE sensor deployments no later than 12 hours after landing.

Deployments will require the application of LuSEE operational power by the Lander PDU. The LuSEE internal protected deployment power bus shall be activated for the deployments, while the MEP is powered, producing telemetry, and receiving instrument commands,

LuSEE shall design and operate an internal deployment bus interface such that the five (5) LuSEE deployment circuits are protected from accidental or premature firing.

Working with the Lander's MOC, LuSEE SOC personnel will conduct deployments of the LuSEE appendages. This will involve sending low latency near-real-time command procedures to prepare for each step in the deployment process. In coordination with the Lander MOC personnel, the LuSEE team shall be responsible for sending commands to activate the internal deployment safety power bus and the individual deployment commands.

5.3 EARLY OPERATIONS

On the lunar surface, with its appendages deployed, LuSEE will enter its initial daytime operational phase. This will involve the continuous observation of the radio sky.

Telemetry data (not low latency – not real-time) will be sent by the LuSEE MEP to the Lander and eventually to the MOC from which it will flow to the LuSEE SOC.

The LuSEE SOC expects to receive telemetry data in conjunction with the Lander-earth contact schedule. Notional contact times are apt to be about 12 hours apart. The Lander shall transfer LuSEE telemetry data to the ground with minimal latency, nominally at each ground contact.

The rate at which LuSEE telemetry data are sent to the Lander CDH can be controlled by the LuSEE SOC with ground-based telecommands. The LuSEE MEP is equipped with a large non-volatile memory such that LuSEE telemetry can be acquired and stored internally. Telemetry data is then buffered internally by the LuSEE MEP. Buffered telemetry data can then be played back at commandable bit-rates to the Lander CDH upon command.

LuSEE SOC personnel will collect and analyze telemetry. Based on the received telemetry data itself and a pre-planned LuSEE operations schedule, LuSEE personnel will formulate daily operational plans and build command loads.

Personnel in the LuSEE SOC will provide command loads to the MOC. The MOC will eventually forward the commands to the Lander and then to the LuSEE instrument, where they will be acted upon or installed in the instrument's stored command table for later execution.

The LuSEE SOC will provide command loads in conjunction with the Lander-earth contact schedule. Notional contact times are apt to be about 12 hours apart. The Lander shall uplink LuSEE command loads with minimal latency, nominally at each ground contact.

5.4 TRANSITION TO SCIENCE OPERATIONS

As part of the first day of operations, LuSEE will transition to using its internal systems for power generation and for communications. As the sun sets at the end of the first lunar day, the Lander batteries will drain and the Lander's daytime mission will end.

Using LuSEE specific solar panels and the LuSEE internal power system, the LuSEE internal battery system will be fully charged. LuSEE will begin operations from its internal power system. LuSEE will stop its use of the Lander power system.

Using the internal LuSEE User-Terminal transceiver, telemetry data (not low latency – not real-time) will be transmitted by the LuSEE internal transceiver to the orbiting relay spacecraft and eventually to the orbiter MOC from which it will flow to the LuSEE SOC. LuSEE will stop its use of the Lander communications system.

Based on the received telemetry data itself and a pre-planned LuSEE operations schedule, LuSEE personnel will formulate daily operational plans and build command loads.

Personnel in the LuSEE SOC will provide command loads to the Orbiter MOC. Those commands will eventually be radiated to the orbiting relay spacecraft and then to the LuSEE internal transceiver on the surface where they will be acted upon or installed in the LuSEE stored command table for later execution.

LuSEE requires that, as the sun sets at the end of the first lunar day, the Lander and all of its other subsystems will permanently cease all operations. This shall include quiescing Lander subsystems throughout the lunar night. This shall include ensuring that all lunar subsystems remain inactive when the sun rises at the end of the first and all subsequent lunar nights.

5.5 SCIENCE OPERATIONS DURING LUNAR NIGHT

On the lunar surface, with its appendages deployed and operating independently from the Lander, LuSEE will enter its night operations phase. This will involve the continuous observation of the radio sky.

Having configured its antenna subsystem (in terms of theta and phi angles) during the previous lunar day, LuSEE will remove power from its antenna actuation system.

Having received its night operations schedule and time synchronization during communication contacts during the previous lunar day, LuSEE will remove power from its User-Terminal transceiver subsystem.

LuSEE will configure itself for night operations. LuSEE will monitor operating voltages and currents throughout the night operations to ensure safe operations that maximize scientific return.

LuSEE will begin continuous observation of the radio sky. Data will be acquired throughout the lunar night. Digital signal processing will produce a stream of averaged spectral data that will be recorded in LuSEE non-volatile memory throughout the night.

As the sun rises at the start of the next lunar day, LuSEE will transition to its daytime operations.

5.6 SCIENCE OPERATIONS DURING LUNAR DAY

On the lunar surface, with its appendages deployed and operating independently from the Lander, LuSEE will enter its day operations phase. This will involve the continuous observation of the radio

sky. Day-time observations will generally be of lower priority than night-time observations but will be useful in terms of instrument operations.

As the sun rises and when LuSEE power levels allow it, LuSEE will apply power to its User-Terminal transceiver subsystem. LuSEE will then answer hails from the orbiting relay spacecraft as defined by the orbiter's contact schedule. As the orbiter contact schedule allows, LuSEE will receive CCSDS telecommand data sent from the LuSEE SOC through the orbiter. The notional telecommand volume to LuSEE is expected to be small. As the orbiter contact schedule allows, LuSEE will send telemetry data to the LuSEE SOC through the orbiter. The notional telemetry to be returned through the relay spacecraft is to be 10GB per lunar cycle (28 earth days).

Based on planning and data obtained from previous night observing periods, the LuSEE SOC will send commands to configure the LuSEE antenna subsystem (in terms of theta and phi angles) during the lunar day.

Based on planning and data obtained from previous night observing periods, the LuSEE SOC will send a stored command table set of commands to be used in night operations during the following lunar night.

LuSEE will configure itself for day operations. LuSEE will monitor operating voltages and currents and battery charging throughout day-time operations to ensure safe operations that maximize scientific return.

As the sun sets at the end of the lunar day, LuSEE will transition to its night-time operations.

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